

Teaching Evaluation Questionnaire

Module Name CQC Final year research project

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	<i>Satisfied</i>	<i>Slightly</i>	<i>Not satisfied</i>
During the module/unit the lecturer:			
1 Whether you have developed the independent work ability after completing the whole project.	☒	☐	☐
2 Are you satisfied with your supervisor.	☒	☐	☐
3 Have you developed the skills in scientific oral presentation.	☒	☐	☐
4 Have you developed the skills in scientific paper writing.	☒	☐	☐
5 Have you finished a nice literature review.	☒	☐	☐
6 Do you like the literature review training.	☒	☐	☐
7 Have you developed you experimental skills.	☐	☐	☒
8 After the program lecture, whether you have fully understand the whole program.	☒	☐	☐
9 Do you like this communication group work mode?	☒	☐	☐
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